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List of Abbreviations

B2B	business-to-business
CO	confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FGD	focus group discussion
F2F	founder-to-founder
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering
H2020	Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union
KPI	key performance indicator
MiR	Makers-in-Residency
MOOC	massive open online course
OERs	open educational resources
OCBM	Open Catalogue of Business Models
PSS	People and Skills Specification
PU	public
RE	restricted
WP	work package
Y1	project year one
Y2	project year two
Y3	project year three

Executive summary

This document, titled Impact Assessment Package, has been developed within the framework of the mAKE project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No. 101016858.

The main goal of this document is to provide the diversified stakeholders involved in the mAKE project with a measuring method and "easy to use" toolkit to continue assessing the project's impact on makers, makerspaces and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem, like political decision makers, investors, etc. The package consists of a description of the logic model, an instrument to conceptualise, plan and track impact assessment, and an example how we applied it in the mAKE project. It provides a set of impact metrics that we used for mAKE to capture the output of core project activities and how they can be attributed to different levels of reach. It gives examples for evaluation instruments that help to collect feedback on resources and training provided by mAKE. And finally shows examples how the data from evaluation and impact assessment can be presented.

The metrics, instruments and presentation modes presented in this document have been proved as being useful and well applicable throughout the three years project runtime of mAKE.

1. Introduction

This document presents the Impact Assessment Package of the mAKE project. After this short introduction it is structured along the following chapters:

- **Chapter 2: Logic Model – conceptualisation and planning of impact assessment**
Introduces the logic model as an instrument that helps to agree on, monitor and present outputs and outcomes.
- **Chapters 3: Impact metrics**
Provides an introduction into KPIs used by the mAKE project and how we used them to track outputs related to different focus areas and levels of reach.
- **Chapters 4: Instruments to collect evaluation data**
Presents questionnaires and question guidelines used in mAKE to collect feedback on mAKE resources and trainings
- **Chapters 5: Outcome presentation for different audiences**
Shows how we reported the impact to the mAKE funders, and how we worked with impact stories/community voices as well as infographics to reach a broader audience.

2. Logic Model – conceptualisation and planning of impact assessment

Evaluation and impact assessment of complex projects, like mAkE, requires a well-structured planning and constant collaborative discussion of success criteria for different activities. Only if the involved stakeholders agree on what constitutes success for them and how to measure this, the elaboration of evaluation instruments and the data collection can start.

With the aim of defining success criteria for the mAkE project and planning the data collection we made use of the logic model (Kurz & Kubek, 2016). This model gives a systematic overview of logical relationships between the project's planned or implemented activities and expected results and includes a formative evaluation — a determination of the extent to which the project is on track, and which fine-tuning activities should be implemented—as well as summative evaluation at the end of the project.

The illustration in Figure 1 below shows the basic elements of the logic model, which distinguishes between inputs/resources, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impact:

- inputs/resources: all necessary inputs devoted to realising the project's objectives, such as efforts, material; or equipment
- activities: what the project does with the resources like events, tools, workshops, actions - the activities should bring out the desired change
- outputs: services and products offered by and resulting from the project like the number of services and actions implemented

The activities and outputs are important for the project's outcomes and impact, and for that reason, the progression from the outputs to the outcomes and impact is crucial for the project's success.

Figure 1: Overview of logic model, adapted from Kurz and Kubek (2016)

In mAKE, during the first 12 months of the project, the evaluation team drafted a logic model matrix for each of the mAKE work packages, for the purposes of regular online reflection meetings with mAKE work package leaders. These matrices were refined by WP leaders during the reflection meetings to be more adapted to the project context - combining the output and impact in one field. As the inputs are in the hands of the project management, this category was left out of the WP matrices, with the focus being on analysing tasks, outputs,

outcomes, and impacts. Also, for optimal planning of evaluation activities, a column was included for capturing potential means of data gathering, and another column was provided for reflections on associated risks and assumptions.

The evaluation matrices served the project team to

- agree on outputs and outcomes
- reflect on stakeholders that need to be involved to collect feedback and evidence for the project evaluation
- think of potential evaluation instruments and time points to collect data
- have the risks and assumptions in mind when planning the impact assessment
- monitor outputs and outcomes
- report about outputs and outcomes

This approach can be adapted to other contexts - e.g. the context of a makerspace organisation. Then one would probably not talk about “work packages”, nevertheless the evaluation planning would need to consider a set of activities/tasks, expected outputs, outcomes and means of data gathering that need to be agreed upon with different stakeholders and task leaders.

In such a way the logic model is not only an instrument to agree on and monitor a set of outputs and outcomes, but also to explore instruments and time points for collecting evaluation data.

Table 1: Overview of logic model template

title	planned activities	engaged actors	expected outcomes /impact	measures /indicators	means of data gathering	risks/assumptions
task1	description
task2	description

To show more concretely how such a model could look like, please find in the following table an evaluation model filled with exemplary content (Table 2).

Planned activities, expected outcomes and how to collect feedback from the stakeholders involved

Outputs are products or services resulting from the planned activities (e.g. workshops, participants in the workshops, etc.)
Outcomes are the effects of the outputs on the target group (e.g. a behaviour change, an increase in knowledge or skills, etc.)

Table 2: Example of logic model usage

Planned activities/tass	Engaged actors	Expected outputs and outcomes	Measures/ indicators	Potential evaluation instruments	Potential risks
<p>Document and disseminate an Open Catalog of Business Models</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Successful businesses, which generate revenue, as well as economic and social impact (will be interviewed), - other organizations involved in supporting business start ups (e.g. training organisation) - Other startups and makerspaces (are provided with access to the catalog), - Other projects and initiatives having done work on this (e.g. OpenNext: catalog of open business models) 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Database of Business Models: Documentation of how existing successful businesses and makerspaces are operating as examples to other early stage start-ups as well as profitable makerspace - Builds on what already exists but is different in the way it is documented and presented, to be really used and applied by start-ups <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inspiration & Increased practical knowledge about different successful business models for start-ups and makerspaces - Practical application of knowledge by startups and makerspaces 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of published example business models of hardware DIHs and ventures - No. of interviews, representing a cross-section of sectors, geographic focus and scale - No. of people accessing and downloading the OCBM - No. of people taking part in the webinars <p>Outcome</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Perceived usefulness of the business model catalog - Lessons learned on how the catalog is used by startups, which information they take out of it, and how they apply it. - No. of business models applied by local businesses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access statistics, social media statistics - Pre-testing and peer-review by “friendly makerspaces” - Interviews with startups and makerspaces who make use of the catalog 	<p>Assumption: We can identify the requested number of businesses who are successful and willing to talk about their business model with us</p> <p>We find startups and makerspaces who are willing to reflect about the usefulness and applicability of the catalog with us and how they use the knowledge presented there</p>

Planned activities/tass	Engaged actors	Expected outputs and outcomes	Measures/ indicators	Potential evaluation instruments	Potential risks
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhanced networking between successful businesses and other startups 			
<p>Creation of a Common Policy Agenda for makerspaces in Africa and Europe</p> <p>Organisation of “Minister meet Makers” events to disseminate the policy agenda</p>	<p>Policy makers at local, regional, national and international level</p> <p>DIHs associations and support structures for makerspaces</p> <p>Makerspaces and DIHs</p>	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-created recommendations (common policy agenda) for policy makers how to foster DIHs and local innovation ecosystems - Organisation of “Minister meet Makers” events to reflect on the policy recommendations <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased knowledge how to support the interface between DIHs, makerspaces interfaces, policy makers, corporates and funders - Increased awareness amongst policy makers about the impact of makerspaces for local communities - Better understanding amongst policy makers how to support makerspaces/DIHs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of policy recommendations published - No. of people accessing/downloading the policy recommendations - No. of events with policy makers (“Ministers meet Makers”) - No. of participants in the events - No. of policy makers attending the meeting - No. of requests for the policy brief - Reference to the events and the recommendations in social media <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Perceived usefulness and applicability of the events and the policy recommendations - Lessons learned about the relationship building between policy makers and makerspaces 	<p>Access statistics and social media statistics</p> <p>Collection of feedback on the first version of the policy agenda</p> <p>Impact pathway interviews with policy makers and makerspaces making use of the policy agenda</p>	<p>Assumption:</p> <p>We succeed in getting policy makers’ interest so that they reflect on the recommendations with us</p>

3. Impact metrics

In the following table we provide important project KPIs that we used in mAkE to track the performance of the project. mAkE is a support action for makerspaces in Africa and Europe with a strong focus on supporting makerspaces and DIHs in increasing financial sustainability, driving policy advocacy and supporting distributed manufacturing. These core areas are reflected in the indicators chosen for the projects.

For follow up activities of mAkE, by e.g. a makerspace organisation, maybe not all of these focus areas are important – so the following set of indicators is a source of inspiration to be adapted to the specific objectives and context of the organisations applying them.

Important to mention is also that KPIs are one part of project evaluation – but many impacts can not only be expressed by numbers but presented in qualitative terms by impact stories and qualitative metrics.

3.1. KPIs for different focus areas

Table 3: Project KPIs

KPIs	Ways to collect data
Venture building and financial sustainability	
No. of supported makerspaces or startups in venture building	Count makerspaces and start-ups that participate in venture buildings activities
No. of hours of venture building and training delivered	Count the hours of venture building support provided to makerspaces and start-ups
Access to the Venture Building Handbook	Count the number of people accessing the Venture Building Handbook online

Access to the Open Business Model Catalogue	Count the number of people accessing the Open Business Model Catalogue online
Business models applied by local businesses	Get feedback from makerspaces who worked with the Business Model Catalogue (i.e. during makerspace gatherings, in workshops or via interview) and find out how many applied their knowledge from the OBMC
Policy advocacy	
No. of meetings, conferences, workshops, 1:1 meetings etc. with policy makers at local, national and international level	Count the number of events
Policy makers attending meetings	Count the number of policy makers that have been actively participating in one of the events
Requests for and access to the policy briefs (e.g. downloads)	Count the number of people accessing the Open Policy Agenda, count the no. of printed Policy Agendas distributed during events
Trainings for makerspaces	
People per year accessing the mAKE-MOOC online platform	Count the number of people accessing the mAKE MOOC
New learning resources on the mAKE MOOC	Count the number of new modules in the mAKE MOOC
People accessing the Open Makerspace Toolkit	Count the number of people accessing the Open Makerspace Toolkit

Training and capacity building events	Count the number of training events organised for makerspaces
Participants in Training and capacity building events	Count the number of participants in the training and capacity building events
Distributed manufacturing	
Entries in the Map of Machinery	Count the number of entries in the Map of Machinery
People testing the Digital Contracting System	Count the number of people involved in testing new versions of the digital contracting system
People using the open standard for maker skills (Maker Passport)	Count the number of people registering to the Maker Passport
Communication and outreach	
Website page views	Count the number of page views, relate page views to events participation, is there growing activity observable?
No. of online and offline events	Count the number of events organised or contributed to
Nof of participants to these events	Count the number of participants to these events, track if events attract people with different socio-demographic backgrounds
Views across all social media channels	Count the number of views on social media, relate them to posts to see what attracts most

	interest
Posts on social media	Count the number of posts to monitor the continuously of contributions to your stakeholders via social media
Followers across all social media	Count the number of followers on social media as an indicator for the attractiveness of your topics, events, posts etc.

3.2. KPIs for different levels of reach

Another interesting way of working with KPIs in the mAKE project, was splitting them up into different levels of reach, e.g.:

- Indicators that showed how individual makers benefited from mAKE (**micro level**),
- Indicators that relate to the outputs and outcomes of makerspaces, start-ups and DIHs (**meso level**)
- Indicators that show the benefits for community representatives like political decision makers (**macro level**). This division provides a more fine-tuned view on impact areas of follow-up activities.

An example is provided in the following table together with some **outcomes and qualitative metrics** that were the result of applying the **outputs (KPIs)**.

Table 4: Project KPIs at micro, meso and macro level

	Micro level (individual makers, innovators, etc.)	Meso level (makerspaces, DIHs, startups, etc.)	Macro level (associations, networks, policy level, etc.)
Key outputs	<p>Individual participants actively involved in co-designing, shaping and using the mAKE outputs</p> <p>Open Makerspace Toolkit and Training-of-Trainers: Open Makerspace Toolkit downloaded 309 times Planning and organising of 5 training-of-trainers event with overall 74 participants</p> <p>mAKE infrastructure developed and tested: Prototype of PSS/Maker Passport system developed (M18) 45 makers sign up for the PSS/Maker Passport</p>	<p>DIHs/makerspaces, startups and SMEs and other relevant stakeholders actively involved in co-designing, shaping and using the mAKE outputs</p> <p>Venture building programme and handbook: 20 companies selected for Venture Building programme 130 hours of Venture Building provided 3 pitch training workshops 1 Venture Building Handbook in English and French version created and downloaded over 400 times 21 makerspace representatives attending the Venture Building Training-of-Trainer</p> <p>mAKE Open Business Model Catalogue created, tested and shared: 17 published business models, in Open Catalogue of Business Models 10 makerspaces involved in a mentoring programme using the OCBM 10 makerspaces applying the business models</p> <p>mAKE digital Infrastructure developed and tested: 9 makerspaces tested PSS/Maker Passport prototype, Map of Machinery and the digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing 20,000 records and 10,308 unique entries in the Map of Machinery</p>	<p>Political decision-makers and representatives of DIH associations involved in co-designing, shaping, using the mAKE outputs</p> <p>mAKE events to create and discuss policy agenda and recommendations: 69 participants in 11 focus group discussions and 7 interviews 11 events attended by mAKE to share the Common Policy Agenda: 400 participants from stakeholders, amongst them 42 policy makers</p> <p>mAKE resources created and shared: Common Policy Agenda and Recommendations for Policy Makers completed and downloaded 368 times Approximately 100 printed policy brief share Over 850 social media reach</p>

Intermediate outcomes	<p>Capacity building and knowledge gains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased knowledge on how to set up, manage and equip DIHs and makerspaces Mutual learning between involved makers and makerspaces <p>Increased collaboration and mutual learning between makers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Through all the mAKE events and community building Through the different mentoring and ToT programmes Through the new relationships created in the mAKE project <p>Strong community building in the African makerspace community and relationship building between European and African makers</p>	<p>Capacity building and knowledge gains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased practical knowledge about different successful business models Increased knowledge and understanding on Venture Building and options running makerspaces more sustainably Increased knowledge and awareness about distributed manufacturing and the digital contracting systems <p>Practical steps towards higher sustainability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased sustainability through newly applied business models SMEs/startups in the Venture Building programme able to make it to the next stage of venture building 60,000 Euro secured funding and 3 million Euro pending funding opportunities from the Venture Building programme <p>Co-creation of mAKE infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning about key aspects like quality control and the diversity of roles required. <p>Facilitated finding of manufacturing sites for open-source projects and more efficient and collaborative local production</p>	<p>Capacity building and knowledge gains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning about policy requirements and recommendations of makerspaces/DIHs Increased knowledge of how to support DIHs in the different national contexts <p>Strengthened relationships:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthened relationships between policy makers and makers <p>Commitment and awareness amongst policy makers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced awareness about the impact of makerspaces amongst policy makers Increased commitment of government officials to support the agenda <p>Inclusion of more African members in DIH/makerspace networks</p>
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3.3. Impact assessment for makerspaces

The assessment of the impact of makerspaces was not the focus of the mAKE project. But there is interesting work on the evaluation and impact assessment of makerspaces conducted by a former mAKE consortium member, Getrude Goh. In her work, she suggested a number of important KPIs for makerspaces to evaluate their outputs. For further reading please follow the link:

https://cdn.prod.website-files.com/5f6cebb6de4bd5618ec097ff/6491a3d305066299098fdb1_Report%20on%20Makerspace%20Impact%20Indicators%20-%20Final%20Draft%20of%20IMA%20Deliverable.pdf

Figure 2: Makerspaces lead to impacts, taken from G. Goh's report on impact assessment for makerspaces

4. Instruments to collect evaluation data in a very practical context

This chapter introduces data collection instruments that proved to be easily applicable in the mAKE project and provided interesting insights for the project evaluation. We learned throughout the project that we operate in a context where we have to make use of “low-key” data collection instruments that demand only little effort and time to be filled in. That’s why we worked with short questionnaires. Also interviews worked well, as participants just needed to provide their time for the interview but did not need to write down or document their experiences.

Thus evaluation instruments needed to be easy to use and less detailed as they would probably be in a more research-oriented setting. For mAKE it was important to collect feedback from the involved makers, makerspaces, DIHs and startups, policy makers etc. and evaluation instruments needed to be simple and very much to the point - focusing on a number of key questions that are most important for evaluation.

In the following paragraphs you will find some examples of questionnaires and question guidelines:

4.1. Questionnaires

4.1.1. Venture Building Handbook Questionnaire:

The questionnaire to collect feedback on the Training-of-Trainers related to the Venture Building Handbook was set up online via Google-Forms. <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScsdC0NKjVsk3aOAY7AdYzmeIOI2wYbaF4cnxHI0jGd-KWhg/viewform>

mAKE Train-the-Trainer feedback

Thank you for having participated in our Train-the-Trainer program. Please take the 3 minutes to provide feedback on the training.
This is important for us to learn about it's usefulness and to understand what is still needed to better support digital innovation and local production.

teresaholocher@gmail.com [Switch account](#)

Not shared

* Indicates required question

Name *

Your answer

Please indicate how much the following statements apply for this event.

	Fully disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Fully agree
The topic of Venture Building is highly relevant for me.	<input type="radio"/>				
There was highly practical knowledge provided.	<input type="radio"/>				

I learned something important in this training.

There was a lot of reflection and exchange with other attendees.

What did you like best? *

Your answer

How do you intend to use the new knowledge? *

Your answer

What additional support is needed to help makerspaces and the startups within them succeed in Venture Building-related areas? *

Your answer

Do you have concrete suggestions for improvement of the online-training for us?

Your answer

What is your profile? (multiple answers possible) *

- FabLab manager
- Trainer
- Entrepreneur
- Innovator
- Maker/hacker
- Engineer
- Software developer
- Scientist
- Funder
- Policy maker
- Student
- Other: _____

Have you had a chance to explore the Venture Building Handbook yet? *

- Yes
- No

How would you rate the usefulness of the Venture Building Handbook in supporting your companies, makerspace or project development? *

1 2 3 4 5

Not useful Extremely useful

What initial impacts have you experienced after reviewing the Venture Building Handbook?

Increased awareness of key topics

Gained new knowledge

Fresh ideas for approaching Venture Building

First steps taken in your startup process

Other: _____

Please share a few words about your experience with the Venture Building Handbook, including any new insights or actions it inspired.

Your answer _____

Have you connected with your "class mates"? *

Yes

Not yet but I will

No

4.1.2. Venture Building Programme Questionnaire:

Also the questionnaire to collect feedback on the Venture Building Programme was provided online via Google Forms to participants:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScvyUuO4nczfgusxfMK8PV2K0AhMuGmwAMwPnSNCBjo2i_dQQ/viewform

mAKE Venture Building feedback

Thank you for having participated in our Venture Building program. Please take the 3 minutes to provide feedback on the training.
This is important for us to learn about it's usefulness and to understand what is still needed to better support European and African ventures.

teresaholoher@gmail.com [Switch account](#)

Not shared

* Indicates required question

Name of your company

Your answer _____

Please indicate how much the following statements apply for the Venture Building * trainings:

	Fully disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Fully agree
There was highly practical knowledge provided.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learned something important during the trainings	<input type="radio"/>				

There was a lot of reflection and exchange with other attendees.

The training helped me to clarify my business strategy.

The training supported me in clarifying my value proposition.

Do you feel confident to further apply the knowledge from the venture building programme?

Based on your experience, what should we improve in future venture building trainings? *

Your answer

Can you share any recent experiences that have influenced your activities as a result of the participation in the venture building programme? *

Your answer

How do you think your activities will be influenced in the next months as a result of the venture building programme? *

Your answer

How satisfied are you with the overall support provided by the program? *

- Very satisfied
- Satisfied
- Neutral
- Dissatisfied
- Very dissatisfied

Any training other session you would have liked to receive?

Your answer

Have you secured any funding or initiated discussions with investors since January 2024? Preferably in Euro or USD. *

Your answer _____

Have you begun any cooperation, partnership, project, or other type of collaboration with the other cohort startups, or are you still in touch and exchanging ideas? *

Your answer _____

Have you had a chance to explore the Venture Building Handbook yet? *

Yes

No

How would you rate the usefulness of the Venture Building Handbook in supporting your startup or project development? *

1 2 3 4 5

Not useful

Extremely useful

What initial impacts have you experienced after reviewing the Venture Building Handbook?

- Increased awareness of key topics
- Gained new knowledge
- First steps taken in your startup process
- Fresh ideas for approaching Venture Building
- Other: _____

Please share a few words about your experience with the Venture Building Handbook, including any new insights or actions it inspired.

Your answer

Thank you for your feedback!

Submit

Clear form

4.1.3. Training-of-Trainers Questionnaire:

The questionnaire to collect feedback on the Training-of-Trainers related to the Open Makerspace Toolkit was distributed online via Google Forms and had both English and French questions:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSd33rXdVbYkzO17wGvdEHihwGRI7oAo7QuPtYj4ddfQq_vHuQ/vi^{ewform}

mAKe Train-the-Trainer feedback

Thank you for having participated in our Train-the-Trainer event on the open makerspace toolkit. Please take the 5 minutes to provide feedback on the training.

This is important for us to learn about it's usefulness and to understand what is still needed to better support digital innovation and local production.

FR:
Merci d'avoir participé à notre événement de formation des formateurs sur la boîte à outils des MakerSpace. Veuillez prendre 5 minutes pour donner votre avis sur la formation. Cela nous permet d'en savoir plus sur son utilité et de comprendre ce qui reste à faire pour mieux soutenir l'innovation numérique et la production locale.

teresaholocher@gmail.com [Switch account](#)

 Not shared

In which of the following trainings have you participated?

FR
À laquelle des formations suivantes avez-vous participé

- Train-the-Trainer in Cameroon || Formation des formateurs au Cameroun
- Train-the-Trainer in Ivory Coast || Formation des formateurs en Côte d'Ivoire
- Train-the-Trainer in Germany || Formation des formateurs en Allemagne?
- Train-the-Trainer, AfricaOSH summit in Accra || Formation des formateurs, Sommet AfricaOSH à Accra

Please indicate how much the following statements apply for this event.||

Veillez indiquer dans quelle mesure les énoncés suivants s'appliquent à cet événement.

Fully disagree En désaccord total.	Disagree En désaccord.	Undecided Indécis.	Agree D'accord.	Fully agree Tout à fait d'accord
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The topic of this event is highly relevant for me.|| Le sujet de cet événement est très pertinent pour moi.

<input type="radio"/>				
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There was highly practical knowledge provided.|| Des connaissances très pratiques ont été transmises.

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I learned something important in this event.||J'ai appris quelque chose d'important lors de cet événement.

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

There was a lot of reflection and exchange with other attendees. || Il y a eu beaucoup de réflexions et d'échanges avec les autres participants.

The training materials (manuals, presentations, etc.) and activities were effective in helping me learn how to deliver the training. || Les supports de formation (manuels, présentations, etc.) et les activités étaient efficaces pour m'aider à apprendre à dispenser la formation.

Please indicate how much the following statements apply for the open makerspace toolkit.

Veillez indiquer dans quelle mesure les déclarations suivantes s'appliquent à la boîte à outils des makerspace.

Fully disagree En désaccord total.	Disagree En désaccord.	ndecided Indécis.	Fully agree Tout à fait d'accord
---	----------------------------	-------------------------	---

The open makerspace toolkit contains very relevant information for makers, innovators and entrepreneurs. ||
La boîte à outils des espaces de création ouverte contient des informations très pertinentes pour les créateurs, les innovateurs et les entrepreneurs.

<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I think the content is applicable in the context I am working in. || Je pense que le contenu est applicable dans le contexte dans lequel je travaille.

<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I intent to spend more time reading through the makerspace toolkit. || J'ai l'intention de passer plus de temps à lire la boîte à outils des MakerSpace

I will show the makerspace toolkit to my colleagues. || je vais montrer la boîte à outils des Makerspace à mes collègues.

For me the most relevant information in the toolkit is:

Pour moi, l'information la plus pertinente dans la boîte à outils est :

Your answer

How do you intend to use the new knowledge of the open makerspace toolkit? ||

Comment comptez-vous utiliser les nouvelles connaissances acquises sur la boîte à outils des makerspace ?

Your answer

Do you feel prepared to adapt the training content to the specific needs of your audience? ||

Vous sentez-vous prêt à adapter le contenu de la formation aux besoins spécifiques de votre public ?

Yes / Oui

No / Non

What additional support is needed for digital innovation and local smart production? ||

Quel soutien supplémentaire est nécessaire pour l'innovation numérique et la production locale intelligente ?

Your answer

Do you have concrete suggestions for improvement of the toolkit for us?//

Avez-vous des suggestions concrètes pour améliorer la boîte à outils à notre intention ?

Your answer

What is your profile? (multiple answers possible) || Quel est votre profil ? (plusieurs réponses possibles)

Innovator

Maker/hacker

Engineer // Ingénieur

Software developer // Développeur de logiciels

Scientist // Scientifique

Funder // Bailleur de fonds

Entrepreneur

Policy maker // Décideur politique

Student

Other: _____

Thank you for your feedback! //
Merci pour votre avis!

Submit Clear form

4.1.4. Policy Recommendations Questionnaire:

The questionnaire to collect feedback on the usefulness of the Policy Recommendations collected feedback online via Google Forms:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSesAlqJ0cXkKvHiwQsUceCtypo8HBnHG9Yqyfb_Bi6INMXn5g/vie wform

Policy Recommendations for Makerspaces

Shaping the Future of Makerspaces in Africa and Europe

mAKE Policy Recommendations for the Maker Movement - Feedback Form

The form is designed to gather feedback from maker movement stakeholders—i.e., representatives of, and participants in, makerspaces, fab labs and other Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs)—regarding the relevance of the mAKE project’s common policy agenda.

[Common Policy Agenda: Recommendations for Policy Makers.](#)

[mAKE](#) is the African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem project, funded by the EU.

Kindly share the [Common Policy Agenda: Recommendations for Policy Makers](#) with your networks, and please help us to gather more feedback by tagging the [mAKE project](#) on social media or cc'ing us (josephagyina@outlook.com and freda@fab.city) when you share via email.

To learn about the various types of stakeholders involved in the Common Policy Agenda and what we can ask of them, please access this [Common Policy Agenda Engagement Guide](#). Among many other things, the Guide includes a case study highlighting how an association in Kenya is actively working to make the country’s Startup Bill become law.

teresaholocher@gmail.com [Switch account](#)

Not shared

* Indicates required question

What is your profile? (multiple answers possible) *

- Makerspace founder
- Makerspace manager
- Makerspace representative
- Makerspace community member
- Non-governmental organisation/foundation/network
- Education/research
- Government and policy
- Suppliers and vendors
- Students/vendors
- Other: _____

Country of operation *

Your answer _____

What is your first impression of the Common Policy Agenda? *

Your answer _____

These policy recommendations, if taken up by policy makers, have the potential to * improve the work of makerspaces/fab labs/DIHs.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

To what extent do these policy recommendations address the specific needs of * your makerspace/fab lab/DIH?

Your answer

Which, if any, elements do you feel should be added to the Common Policy Agenda?

Your answer

How likely are you to share the common policy agenda in your networks? *

Very unlikely
 Unlikely
 Neutral
 Likely
 Very Likely

With whom do you intent to share the policy recommendations? Eg., Minister of Science and Technology, Minister of Education, etc., *

Your answer _____

Is there any advice, of any sort, that you wish to pass on to the mAKE team working on policy matters?

Your answer _____

Email address (If you'd like us to engage with you beyond this form, please add your email address here)

Your answer _____

Submit Clear form

4.2. Question guidelines

When conducting interviews, there are some basic considerations to consider:

- Send questions before the interview to the interviewee to be able to prepare and clarify any uncertainties
- Start the interview with an introduction to the purpose of the interview and usage of data:
 - Explain why you are doing the interview, how the insights from the interview will be used and how they will be published.

- Ask participants to consent to this usage of their data.
- Explain that you would like to record the interview for better documentation, inform interviewees that recordings and transcripts will be deleted after usage.
- Ask participants to provide consent on the recording, if they don't, you have to write a protocol of the interview.
- Usage of the questions: the prepared questions “guide” the interviewer through the interview to make sure that the main aspects are covered. The order of questions can be changed during the interview, e.g. if the respondent starts to talk about something at the beginning of the interview that would have been asked at the end. If respondents start to bring up other aspects (other than covered by the questions but relevant to your project/activities) don't stop them.

4.2.1. Question guidelines for the Open Catalogue of Business Models:

The following questions were used during online interviews to collect feedback on the usefulness and applicability of the Open Catalogue of Business Models. Interviews were recorded, transcribed and then used for impact stories (see next Chapter):

1. What did you like best about the mentoring programme? And about the OCBM?
2. What were important insights from the programme for you and your makerspace?
3. Do you feel confident to further apply the knowledge from the mentoring programme and the OCBM?
4. Do you think that the mentoring programme and OCMB contributed (or can contribute) to your business running more sustainable or has it influenced your business in any other way? Will you continue to work on your financial sustainability
5. Is there any aspect for you missing in the OCMB or during the mentoring programme? How can we improve it? Is there anything else you would like to share?
6. Have you recommended the OCMB to others?

4.2.2. Question guidelines for the Training-of-Trainers (WP3):

The following interview questions were defined to capture the impact of the Training-of-Trainers related to the Open Makerspace Toolkit. Interviews were conducted online and summarised in the form of impact stories (please see the following Chapter).

1. How did you use the Makerspace Toolkit?
2. What do you think the Makerspace Toolkit and the ToT is useful for?
3. Do you feel confident to further apply the knowledge from the ToT and the toolkit in your makerspace?
4. Do you think that participating in the ToT has influenced your makerspace business in any way?
5. Have you recommended the Toolkit to others?

5. Outcome presentation for different audiences

In this chapter we want to introduce some considerations when presenting data from evaluation and impact assessment.

5.1. Reports for Funders

In mAkE the key audience for the impact assessment was the European Commission as funding organisation: So, our Interim and Final Impact Assessment Reports to the EC were the main outcomes of the work. Follow the following two links, if you want to get an idea how we reported about the mAkE impacts via two reports.

D7.2. Interim Impact Assessment Report: <https://zenodo.org/records/14792990>

D7.3. Final Impact Assessment Report: <https://zenodo.org/records/14793178>

5.2. Community Voices/Impact Stories for a broader audience:

In mAkE we did not only want to use the data to report to our funders, but also to communicate with other important stakeholders and get their interest for the work we did, like makers, makerspace managers, political decision makers, investors, founders etc.

With this aim we elaborated impact stories which we called “community voices” in mAkE as this fits better with our stakeholders:

Impact stories show key benefits of using the developed mAkE resources (like the Open Catalogue of Business Models, the Venture Building Handbook, the Policy Agenda or the Training of Trainers) in different contexts.

These stories are built on concrete feedback of early users of our resources, on how they used the newly gained knowledge, how they applied it in their practical context and how others benefited from them as well. They are based on the input which we collected via questionnaires and interviews and are presented in the form of 2 to 4 pagers - easy to read, nicely designed - to be shared on the website, on social media or during events to attract more people to use mAkE outcomes.

With the purpose of working on the impact stories we created a template that is attached in the Annex 1 of this document. And the following visualisations show some examples of mAkE community voices, as this approach proved to be highly efficient to communicate about mAkE and thus highly recommended to organizations continuing the mAkE work.

Community Voices: mentees feedback on the OCBM

Building Financially Sustainable Makerspaces Through the Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM)

As makerspaces continue to inspire innovation and empower communities, financial sustainability remains a key challenge. The **Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM)**, developed through collaborative input from global makerspaces, offers a flexible solution. This “living document” is designed to help makerspaces adapt business strategies that align with their unique objectives, cultural contexts, and community needs. By providing modular business model elements, the OCBM enables makerspaces to craft tailored paths toward sustainability.

The Concept Behind OCBM: A Toolkit, Not a Template

Makerspaces thrive when sharing stories of innovation, learning, and community impact; however, discussions on financial sustainability are typically more reserved.

“We saw the need for something like a buffet – that people running makerspaces can browse through to gain ideas, choosing elements that seem relevant to what they are trying to create. This is the idea behind the OCBM.”

---Anna Sera Lowe, Manufacturing Change Ltd, creator of the OCBM---

Co-Creating the OCBM: Input from a Global Community

The OCBM was co-developed with input from 50 representatives from makerspaces and distributed manufacturing organisations across Africa and Europe, ensuring it reflected a wide spectrum of business models and entrepreneurial insights. The inputs were compiled with the assistance of **Martin Oloo**, CEO of Fablab Winam, and **Gertrude Mawuena Goh**, researcher into the marketing practices of makerspaces.

A Path Forward: Expanding OCBM's Reach

There is strong interest in expanding the programme to include more makerspaces, particularly across Africa. Available at LocalEconomies.org the OCBM is continuously updated, incorporating new insights and case studies to support a diverse array of makerspaces worldwide.

Early Success Stories: OCBM in Action

In 2023, a mentoring programme was launched, inviting makerspaces to explore how to apply elements of the OCBM to achieve financial independence.

Ronald from iZone Hub in Zimbabwe

shared that the mentoring programme was instrumental in his makerspace's journey towards sustainability.

“It was great how flexible the Open Business Model Catalogue was. We could adapt it to the needs of our makerspace. It was not made in stone, but an encouragement and provided new ideas to make small changes that fit in the current systems.”

With guidance from mentors, the team explored alternative revenue streams, such as partnering with organisations to fund training initiatives and offering 3D printing services.

“In one of our sprints, we realised with the support of our mentor that we can try to partner with other organisations to come in and pay for the training. It opened our eyes.”

Eric from Garoua Makerspace in Cameroon

highlighted the value of exchanging experiences with other makerspaces and learning from diverse mentors.

“The best thing was the sharing of experience with other makerspaces from different areas. We started to collect experiences with offering trainings to be able to generate income. The population here is not so open to new technology, but curiosity is growing.”

Michael Danquah from Design and Technology Institute in Ghana

reports that the OCBM supported implementing more structured revenue-generating activities.

“It guided us in creating an online training model for 3D modeling, which helps us expand access to our offerings and attract a broader range of users... It has also helped us refine our approach to community engagement by offering new models like Startup Support.”

Mary Nyamanga of FabLab Winam in Kenya

explains how the OCBM helped to re-evaluate the current business model.

“The OCBM has resulted in re-evaluating our current business model. We are considering implementing complementary models, where we have come up with a price list for different packages, which will help in addressing scalability and financial sustainability.”

Through mentorship, co-creation, and an adaptable toolkit, the OCBM can help to transform makerspaces into financially resilient, impactful hubs for innovation. For further information visit LocalEconomies.org or contact anna@manufacturingchange.org.

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

Community Voices: Participants' feedback on the Venture Building ToT and Handbook

Makerspaces as Catalysts for Business Growth with the mAKE Venture Building Programme

As worldwide hubs of creativity and innovation, makerspaces have the potential of transforming into powerful venture builders, supporting entrepreneurs in developing sustainable, impactful businesses. To strengthen this shift, GreenTec Capital Africa Foundation, developed a **Venture Building Programme and Handbook for makerspaces, digital innovation hubs, startups and SMEs.**

A Comprehensive Venture Building Toolkit

The Venture Building Handbook serves as a practical guide for entrepreneurs, venture builders, and makerspace managers. It outlines 12 critical steps for launching and growing scalable businesses — from idea generation to market research, product development, and networking. This structured approach provides entrepreneurs with both the strategic and operational skills needed for sustainable growth.

"The Venture Building Handbook has given me knowledge about venture building which I never knew before. Most of our Fablab activities are much more on making and building, but with this knowledge, we can now take those innovations into business." – Fablab Manager from Tanzania

12 steps for Venture Builders

1. Idea Generation and Validation	7. Legal and Regulatory Compliance
2. Market Research	8. Sales and Marketing Strategies
3. Business Model Development	9. Scaling and Growth
4. Product Development	10. Networking and Mentorship
5. Team Building and Leadership	11. Exit Strategies
6. Fundraising and financial management	12. Case Studies and Real-World Examples

Access the the Venture Building Handbook in English and French:
makeafricaeu.org
english

french

Community Voices – Venture Building in Action

The handbook places a strong emphasis on user-centric design, a perspective that resonates deeply with entrepreneurs striving to address local needs and challenges.

"The focus on user-centric design was eye-opening. It emphasized understanding the customer journey deeply, inspiring me to conduct thorough customer feedback sessions and adjust our solutions accordingly." – Fablab Manager from Kenya

The handbook's emphasis on leveraging local resources has also sparked new insights.

"The handbook is enriched with insights that resonate with African businesses... leveraging our local resources, like talents, can be an easy and best way of not just generating but validating the feasibility of an idea." – Fablab Manager from Ghana

It provides makerspaces, entrepreneurs and startups with a frame for self-reflection, personal and corporate development.

"With this new knowledge, I intend to tailor support strategies for startups in makerspaces through 1-on-1 mentorship with founders, hub managers, and trainers. This approach will strengthen connections and foster an ecosystem where startups can access vital resources and collaborative opportunities for growth." – Trainer and Innovator from Tanzania

The handbook also serves as a testing ground for refining one's own business models before bringing these strategies to clients and community members.

"I liked the training content on Financial Analysis and Business Models best and will improve our current model of operations as a result of this knowledge." – Fablab Manager from Tanzania

"I will be my own test case first, fine-tuning the business model for my Hub. With that experience, I will then bring this approach to the organisations and businesses I mentor, coach, and train." – FabLab Manager from Ethiopia

A Path Forward for Makerspaces as Venture Builders

This pillar of the mAKE Venture Building Programme is supporting makerspaces to evolve into venture-building hubs that stimulate local economies and support sustainable business development. If you are interested, find more info on: makeafricaeu.org

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

Community Voices: Makers and Hosts Experiences from the MiR exchange programme

African European Maker
Innovation Ecosystem

The “Makers in Residency”-Programme Sparks Innovation and Collaboration between African and European Makers

The Makers in Residency (MiR) programme has successfully connected African and European makers, fostering a unique blend of knowledge sharing and collaborative innovation. In 2024, the MiR programme supported four emerging hardware innovators from Egypt, Tanzania, and Rwanda, providing a one-month residency in European makerspaces. Each maker worked on ground-breaking projects while benefiting from direct mentorship, access to advanced equipment, and an inspiring environment.

“This initiative aims to break down barriers, create new ideas, and build essential networks between continents.”
---- Fabienne Kirchhof, GreenTec Capital Africa Foundation ----

African European Maker
Innovation Ecosystem

Martine, a maker from Rwanda hosted in Belgium, focused on a sustainable solution to reduce material costs for makers by recycling plastic bottles to create affordable 3D printer filament.

“The timeline was tight, but with the Liege team’s support, we combined our efforts to make it happen.” --- Martine Basaninyage, Makerspace Westerwelle Startup Haus Kigali, Rwanda ---

Martine’s hosts witnessed her dedication and ingenuity, *“We learned so much from her resourcefulness and resilience — she’s building amazing solutions with far fewer resources than we’re used to.”*
--- Loic, Hackerspace Liege, Belgium ---

Asem, a maker from Egypt hosted in France, brought a sense of international community to La Bricothèque Fablab, engaging with local members and sharing his project’s vision and knowledge.

“Asem’s openness to share his work and life experiences made our Fablab feel part of a global network. We saw a natural exchange of ideas and cultural understanding”
--- Olivier, La Bricothèque, France ---

“My impression about this program is positive and eye opening, as someone who has never been to Europe it was amazing seeing such cool places like the textile lab”.
--- Asem Kamal, maker and content creator, Egypt ---

African European Maker
Innovation Ecosystem

Meanwhile, Leonard, a maker from Tanzania hosted in Spain, pursued his vision to build a nano-satellite prototype to inspire African students and makers in STEM. During his residency at Fablab Barcelona, Leonard expanded his network and honed his technical skills with new equipment.

“This programme brought me closer to new knowledge, and I had hands-on experience with different machines that sparked ideas on how I can bring similar technology to Tanzania.”
--- Leonard Shayo, founder of the aerospace startup Olspace ---

His host, Santi from Fablab Barcelona, was equally inspired, noting Leonard’s unstoppable drive: *“He came in saying, ‘I have to learn as much as I can; I want to send a rocket to the moon!’ His determination was infectious.”*
--- Santi, Fablab Barcelona ---

Witness, a Tanzanian maker hosted in France, reflected on how the residency inspired her project management approach and technical work.

“I have been impressed by the makerspace, the organization, the workshops and overall management. This creates a truly inspiring environment for anyone to get creative.”
--- Witness Shingali, Twende Social Innovation Center, Tanzania ---

Although she felt that one month was limited for a complex prototype, Witness returned to Tanzania with a strong foundation, sketches, and collaborative documentation to drive her project forward. This residency programme has not only equipped African makers with new tools and skills but also brought fresh perspectives and cultural insights to the European hosts.

“We documented everything to support Witness’s ongoing work in Tanzania. The collaboration doesn’t end here; we’ll stay connected to help her team scale up.”
--- Matthieu, Ecocentre, France ---

“Through these transformative exchanges, the MiR programme has strengthened a global network of makers committed to using their skills to address real-world challenges, demonstrating the powerful impact of cross-continental collaboration in the maker community.”
--- Kirstin Wiedow, Global Innovation Gathering ---

Further information on makeafricaeu.org

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

5.3. Visualisations of key KPIs for a broader audience:

To support the communication of impact to a broader audience we worked a lot with Infographics in mAKE, please see some examples in the following visualisations.

Figure 3: Infographic Dissemination KPIs

Figure 4: Infographic MiR KPIs

Figure 5: Infographic Founder-to-Founder events

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

6. References

Kurz, B., & Kubek, D. (2016). *Social impact navigator: The practical guide for organizations targeting better results*. PHINEO gAG, Berlin.

https://www.phineo.org/uploads/Downloads/PHINEO_Social_Impact_Navigator.pdf

ANNEX

Impact Story Template

mAKE IMPACT story for WP X

Impact stories bring anecdotal evidence that activities of the mAKE project were successfully organised and led to concrete results for the stakeholders involved. The impact stories amend quantitative data and analysis of synchronised data (e.g. the analysis of set of questionnaires) by very tangible personal stories that show how the project influenced makers, startup, makerspaces, politicians etc.

Stakeholders who have been impacted:

Please select individuals, representing the stakeholders of your WP, that have been involved in your mAKE activities or affected by mAKE in a substantial way (means that we really had the occasion to generate an impact)

Please describe these individuals here – it can be in keywords.

Description of impact:

Please describe what has changed through the mAKE activities:

WHICH activity led to the impact,

WHAT the impact was,

WHY this is an improvement.

Provide as much details as possible (locations, dates, personal quotes, pictures etc),

Please add your first keywords, pictures, quotes etc. here

